

ORGANIZATIONAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF A CREATIVE ENVIRONMENT IN MANAGEMENT ACTIVITIES

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Annotation. In the selection of employees in the leadership activity, trust is given to young personnel with the above qualities and qualities, special attention is paid to searching for capable, talented and talented young people in management activities, regular work with them, training and improvement of their qualifications.

Keywords. Competence, personnel, leadership talent.

Leading personnel play an important role in the comprehensive implementation of public administration. The fate of the democratic changes implemented in the country depends to a large extent on the activities of the people who are in responsible positions in the state and government offices, their attitude to work, human qualities and leadership skills. The leader's competence, selflessness, fairness, initiative, effectiveness, perseverance, inquisitiveness, striving for innovation, demandingness, economic and legal literacy, spiritual maturity, ability to create a healthy and creative environment in the team are different. In the process of economic reforms implemented in our country, the development of production, ensuring the economic stability of organizations and enterprises largely depends on the quality of training leaders and values that meet the requirements of the time. Today, in the context of building a social economy, the training of leaders, the development of their qualifications and the formation of management skills in retraining is a special profession.

Young specialists with the above qualities are trusted in the selection of personnel for management positions, and special efforts are made to find capable, talented and talented young people for management activities, to regularly work with them, to train and improve their skills.

Today, great importance is attached to people's living and working conditions, social issues and lifestyle. It is not for nothing that our honorable president called 2022 the year of "Glorification of human dignity and active neighborhood". The labor productivity of each employee, the effectiveness of his work depends more on his satisfaction with his work, his spiritual and cultural level, healthy and creative environment in the team, life and living conditions.

Today, great importance is attached to psychological factors in the management activities of leaders. Social psychology lessons are held in the training courses of

managerial personnel, in advanced training courses. The position of psychologist has been introduced in many organizations.

Bernard Shaw said that working in a team is a job; desire for work, and desire - rest, leisure. The normative view of the management system is "man - man", where "man" is meant as an object, and "collective" is distinguished as the subject of a team, i.e. team work.

In the process of management, the team must study each employee under his command, make a psychological diagnosis, have the characteristics of social observation, and be able to determine whether the capabilities of the employees are fully compatible with the work they are doing. One of the most important means of maintaining team cohesion and a healthy moral environment in it is the leader's communicability, that is, maintaining all-round communication.

The functional task of the management is primarily assessed by the creation of a system of mutual relations in the joint activities of employees.

Qualitative aspects of the leader: adaptability, leadership, social functions, coordination; communication (openness in the relationship, the ability to persuade people, establishing business relations); Qualities such as resistance to stress are included in the main stage of the leader.

In addition, scientists define 5 qualitative characteristics of a leader in team management in the following order: principledness, fairness, knowledge of the work, competence, demandingness and organizational characteristics.

Respect, reputation - attention is a unit of measure recognized by the society, it is manifested by recognizing and accepting the decisions made by the leader of the team as his opinion and advice. One of the quality aspects of a leader is to deal with creative ideas put forward by the team, rather than with actions taken using his official position. This indicates the ability of the leader to create a healthy and creative environment in the team when managing educational institutions. Therefore, the leader should have a high level of prestige (respect) in accordance with his position and position.

Management is carried out by influencing the team more by being able to direct, convince, and gain confidence in it (democratic style), as well as by forcing through orders (autocratic style).

Success in leadership does not depend on the leader's authority over his position, but on his reputation - position, energy, extensive experience, extensive knowledge, talent, creation of a creative atmosphere in the team, and his intelligence. The democratic style of leadership is the first in both centralized and decentralized management methods. First of all, it leads to an increase in production productivity through a creative approach by solving business problems in a team way. A good leader knows what to do, how to do it, organizes the work correctly, can guide the team towards the goal and achieve an effective result.

Success in management activities is the interest of the leader and the entire team in work, increasing creativity through a healthy environment in the team, high level of organization, and striving to achieve the goal.

One of the important characteristics of leadership skills is to clearly define the tasks of employees, to give them leadership powers and to achieve good results by managing them wisely.

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